
Psycho Social Aspects of Mothers of Children with Intellectual Disability in Relation to Mother Empowerment Program.

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ABSTRACT: The present study investigated the effect of mother empowerment programme on psycho social aspects of mothers having children with intellectual disability attending four special schools of Kottayam district . A descriptive survey cum experimental pretest post test control group research design was used for the study. The objective of the study was to find out the effect of mother empowerment programme on psycho social aspects of mothers having children with intellectual disability. The instrument used for the study was Psycho social scale, pretest was done, mother empowerment programme was given to 50 mothers who obtained low Psycho social score in the survey after obtaining Institutional Ethics Committee approval and permission from the special school authorities. Post test was done using the same instrument, six months after the pre test. The results of ANCOVA showed there is a significant difference in post test Psycho social scores between the experimental and control group. (F = 4.994, P =0.02)

INTRODUCTION

Mothers having children with intellectual disability experience a vast range of emotional, psychological and social problems. Families of these children have greater psycho social impact and experience unhealthy family functioning. (Emerson, 2003). Research have found that most of them experience financial crisis due to treatment expenses of the child and are economically disadvantaged. Hence there is an urgent need to develop complex intervention such as empowerment programmes for mothers in combating poverty and thus earn their livelihood.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Psycho social Aspects of mothers of children with intellectual disability in relation to mother empowerment program in selected special schools of Kottayam District.

OBJECTIVE

- ❖ To find out the psychosocial aspects of mothers of children with intellectual disability.

Operational definitions of key terms

Psychosocial aspects

Refers to various psychological and social aspects influencing mothers of children with intellectual disability covering the following domains such as Psychosocial issues experienced by mothers, Measures used to improve psychological wellbeing of mothers, Social emotional and family problems faced by mothers, Help & support obtained from family, relatives and friends, Financial aspects & financial help obtained from government welfare schemes for children with intellectual disability, Career aspects & opportunities to improve sense of social wellbeing, Aspects of home based care of child with intellectual disability with mother as primary care giver, Counseling services and help obtained to mothers, Feelings of empathy, compassion and affection towards child, Influence of child's siblings measured by the Psycho social scale developed by the investigator.

Mothers

Refers to biological mothers of children with intellectual disabilities attending special schools of Kottayam district recruited to the study.

Children with intellectual disability

Refers to children diagnosed with intellectual disability attending special schools of Kottayam district.

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Mother empowerment program

It refers to a mothers' empowerment program by the formation of mothers' support groups organized in special schools and psycho educational supportive intervention given for 2 hours daily for a period of four consecutive days in six separate sessions, covering the areas of cognitive, psychological, economical and political ways of empowering mothers through group discussion and separate teaching sessions given by the investigator.

HYPOTHESES

- There will be no significant difference in mean post test psychosocial scores between the experimental and control group after the mother empowerment program.

Methods

The study is conducted among 250 mothers of children with intellectual disability attending 12 special schools of Kottayam district, selected via simple random sampling. A descriptive survey cum experimental pretest post test control group research design was used in the study. Instruments used for the study were demographic data sheet and Psycho social scale developed by the investigator. Pre test was done and 50 mothers who obtained low psycho social scores in the pretest were provided with the mother empowerment programme by organizing the mother's support groups in four special schools after obtaining Institutional Ethics Committee clearance. The mother empowerment programme covered 6 separate sessions in 12 hours covering the areas of cognitive, psychological, economical and political ways of empowering mothers through group discussion and separate teaching sessions given by the investigator. Post test was done 6 months after the pre test using the same instrument, Psycho social scale. Data was analysed using SPSS 16.

RESULTS

- It was found that majority (52.40%) of mothers obtained moderate Psycho social score, 36.80 % obtained low Psycho social score and only 10.80 % obtained high Psycho social scores.
- It was found that post test psycho social scores of experimental group improved after the mother empowerment programme.

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage of mothers with respect to their Psycho social level.

Psycho social level	Frequency	Percentage	Possible range of scores
Low	92	36.80	0-30
Moderate	131	52.40	31-58
High	27	10.80	59-100
Total	250	100	0-100

Table 1 shows that 52.40 % of mothers obtained moderate Psycho social score , 36.80 % obtained low Psycho social score and only 10.80% obtained high Psycho social scores.

Table 2. Results of ANCOVA for comparing post test Psycho social scores by taking pre test Psycho social score as covariate among experimental and control group.

Source	df	Type III sum of squares	Mean square	F value	P value	Partial Eta squared
pretest Psycho social score	1	19.218	19.218	1.78	0.18	
Between groups	1	53.890	53.890	4.994	0.02	0.04
Error	97	1046.78	10.79			
Corrected total	99	1115.00				

A one way Analysis of covariance was run to examine whether post test Psycho social scores differed between the experimental and control group while controlling for the pre test psycho social scores. Homogeneity of regression slopes and homogeneity of variance were checked. Pretest Psycho social scores of Experimental and Control groups are similar. $F= 0.685$ Sig=0.410. It is concluded that there is no significant difference between Experimental and Control group as measured by the dependent variable ,that is the pretest Psycho social score.

Leven's test indicated that the assumption of Homogeneity of variance was not violated.

$F(1,98)=0.437$, $P = 0.510$. Homogeneity of Regression slopes is met with a non statistically significant result . $F=2.76$, $P= 0.06$ The slope for pretest Psycho social score means and groups are similar tested by Univariate ANOVA.

A true comparison of difference is done with ANCOVA by taking pretest Psycho social score as covariate . The F value obtained is 4.994 after eliminating the effect of pretest Psycho social scores and is significant at 0.05 level. Hence it is concluded

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that there is a significant difference in post test Psycho social scores between the Experimental and Control groups after the mother empowerment program.

Table 3. Mean values and standard deviations of Psycho social scores of mothers of children with intellectual disability

Test	Group	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Pre test	Experimental	50	26.92	2.456
	Control	50	27.20	2.121
Post test	Experimental	50	34.40	3.220
	Control	50	33.00	3.375

Table 3 indicates mean and standard deviations of the Psycho social scores of mothers. The mean Pre test Psycho social score of the experimental group is 26.92 and that of the control group is 27.20. The mean post test Psycho social score of the experimental group is 34.40 and that of the control group is 33.00

DISCUSSION

The aim of the present study was to find out the effect of mother empowerment programme on Psycho social aspects of mothers having children with intellectual disability. A few studies have analysed the effect of intervention programme on psycho social impact on mothers, in this regard the study findings justify family interventions for the psychological wellbeing of mothers . (Vilaseca et al., 2019).

It was found that 52.40% of mothers obtained moderate Psycho social score, 36.80 % obtained low Psycho social score and only 10.80 % obtained high Psycho social scores. These study findings are congruent with the study conducted by Pahantha Singh et al (2018) on attitude of parents towards children with intellectual disabilities and Psycho social impact on them where 86 % parents have intermediate negative impact on the NIMH Disability Impact scale.

The results of the present study are in agreement with the study conducted by Peshwaria et al (1995) where group parent training model and home based training programmes help in Indian scenario where parents act as mediators and parent support groups help and strengthen families for helping empowering parents. These findings are in congruence with the present study findings

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study highlights the importance of regular counseling sessions and special Parents Teachers Association in the rehabilitation of mothers having children with intellectual disability.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that mother empowerment programme was effective in improving the post test Psycho social scores among the experimental group. Psycho educative supportive intervention given to mothers by organizing mother's support groups helped to improve their Psycho social well being. Hence in this circumstances it is suggested that more parent empowerment programmes need to be given.

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